

USE OF INNOVATIVE METHODS IN MANAGEMENT

Zamanov S.*Nakhchivan State University*<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10629165>**Abstract**

Possibilities of using world experience in administration, the complex feature of state administration and its methodological foundation is that the study of its political-legal, political-social, and socio-economic reality is objective and subjective and at the same time, makes it necessary to benefit from the complex of social-political, theoretical-practical and general-scientific methods in this system. After our country regained its independence on October 18, 1991, fundamental reforms were carried out in state administration, state personnel policy, and the country's economy. In international practice, the central line of the main reforms implemented in the field of civil service is the policy of human resources management. As the Republic of Azerbaijan is a post-Soviet country, traces of administrative management remained in the state administration until recent years. The Republic of Azerbaijan is a legal and democratic state. Democratic state administration is a form of administration based on public trust and people's power. Therefore, the position and opinion of the people and citizens are always important in the professional activities of state managers. This should be considered as a priority direction when civil servants are selected for public bodies and promoted in the service position, and when determining the professional requirements imposed on them. Other nuances to be taken into account when formulating and implementing personnel policy in public administration are the country's socio-political situation, demographic indicators, historical development path, macroeconomic indicators, the country's geographical and political position, quantitative and qualitative changes in the labor market, advanced practices and modern approaches.

Keywords: management in state structures, human resources, civil servants, professional staff, civil service.

Introduction

In Azerbaijan, the main goal of the management method is to create an opportunity to organize the management process correctly and effectively, as well as to effectively use innovative techniques and progressive types of labor and production process organization to fully achieve the goals set by the state. In addition, management methods in the country serve the realization of economic activity and occur in connection with the implementation of management functions in a complex manner. Management methods are considered a method of applying the conditions of the country's strategic progress and economic development laws. Management methods in Azerbaijan are also a form of using laws and principles. With the special selection of these methods in the country, their application varies depending on the nature and content of the managed objects and processes, as well as various events. Three important methods of management are used in Azerbaijan. These are the economic method and the administrative-order method. To achieve management goals in the country, existing economic laws of society are widely used. In addition, taking into account the objective economic benefits and interests, the methods of economic activity are used as economic methods of management. Management with the economic method affects various aspects of the object, i.e. the organization of production, its regulation, the implementation of management activities, the material and moral interests of collectives and their members, and tries to make the production process systematic. Through the economic method used in management, planning, wages, accounting, financial incentives, price, profit, cost, income, and various mechanisms become purposeful tools. Economic methods are aimed at saving the country's resources, re-

ducing its cost, improving the quality of goods and services, increasing the total volume of income and profit, and increasing labor capacity and strength.

Implementation of the administrative-order method used in management activities in Azerbaijan is one of the most important and useful topics. Because it should be used based on the existing laws of the state and society, the labor legislation of the country, as well as the powers given to entrepreneurs with the help of the administrative-order method. In addition, entrepreneurs and specialists who create conditions for the violation of these laws, regulations, and acts are held responsible for these violations. The administrative-discipline method applied in Azerbaijan has a normative-order feature because it is based on the power of the government, therefore its implementation is considered unequivocally mandatory. The main object of the administrative-order method is very wide, and at the same time, it is multifaceted. In the state, the system of organizing the sphere of production, their management organization, the form of labor organization, and management relations with workers are formed and improved by utilizing the administrative-order method.

Public administration methods used in world practice

One of the public administration methods used in world practice is the performance evaluation method. Technological changes in the world, information, the desire of citizens to get more information, and globalization have deeply affected the structure of public administration. With the new concept of public administration, citizen-based, transparent, performance criteria began to dominate the management system of countries. The increase in government spending in countries has increased the importance of performance management aimed at the effective and productive use

of resources. For this purpose, performance management applications have gained importance. For this purpose, means such as standards, goals, and awards are used to ensure that employees in the state are aware of their performance and that the increase in motivation is targeted. When using these management tools, the main goal is to ensure citizen satisfaction.

The performance-based management system is not yet applied in public administration in Azerbaijan. However, this system applied in the USA, Canada, Turkey, and other countries will create conditions for achieving efficiency in public administration in our country. By systematizing individual methods, it should be noted that, as in international practice, understanding and explanation methods in various fields have been improved in state administration, and it is possible to develop a unique research method. It is thought that these methods will be formed over time. Although the important methodological problem - the principle that subjective and objective methods mutually complement each other - is a special method related to the theory of public administration and is very common, differences can be seen in the approaches to its solution.

According to its nature and structure, public administration includes some subjective and objective nuances and approaches. The essence of the method of objective approach in public administration methods explains that the state should not be an outside spectator to itself, to society's demands and wishes, and its activities, it should be able to objectively assess the state of society, as well as the events that cause its concern, the wishes of all members of society, and take steps for this purpose. The subjective method is to look at society as a unit of the state and its management system; it is the method of understanding the problems and difficulties that the society has faced or will face, its desire with its current reality, and paying attention to all these in its management system. The closer these methods are to each other and try to overlap, the more success in public administration can be achieved. Since the development and preparation of other special research methods directly related to the public administration system have not yet taken place, special methods applied in the field of social science related to public administration are used in their form, along with general scientific methods, not only to research numerous problems. The method of analysis and synthesis has an important place among the listed general scientific methods. With the help of these methods, the analysis of various issues related to the subject of this field is carried out, generalization is made, and as a result, general results applicable to public administration are obtained. For example, the composition of the legislative body, the executive body, and the judicial body is determined by the state administration structures and a unified state administration apparatus of the state is formed from their synthesis. The logical judgment method is also widely used in the state administration system. With the help of this method, generalizations, decisions, and opinions of various aspects are formed in intelligence, and then, if necessary, they are reflected in a suitable document and practice. In the public administration system, the

method of formalization is somewhat less used compared to other methods. Through this method, the structure and important directions of the activities of any institution (organization) in statehood and state administration are determined. The comparison method is also seen as one of the widespread methods in the public administration system. Thus, the importance of applying the comparison method in solving the theoretical and practical issues of public administration in the system of statehood is generally accepted, there is no disagreement about this opinion. Acquiring the necessary materials, systematizing them, determining the most important issues, as well as directing the main attention to solving these issues - all these rules are considered the most important condition of correct management. However, there is a difference of opinion regarding which facts to obtain, which facts to compare, and which facts to accept as important in state administration. This diversity of opinion did not belong only to the state administration system. That is, comparing has been important and is used in all fields. In other words, all fields need to compare events, facts, and qualitative and quantitative aspects to obtain concrete results. The quantitative method, as well as forecasting methods with statistical analysis, is one of the most widespread tools in the management system. The role of the forecasting method with quantitative and statistical analysis is important for the improvement of the organizational structure of the management system, in determining the social, political, and economic results that can be shown by the improvement in the decision-making in the management system. Extrapolation and modeling are used as a methodological tool in the management system. Extrapolation is the process of spreading certain positive trends and negative trends in management to similar management organizations. The modeling method is the development and application of various management bodies, management processes, management structures, and operational models. It involves conducting various scientific-theoretical experiments and practices. The method of conducting experiments is used to check the activity of various management organizations/institutes within the established conditions or to study the current situation and prepare some proposals. The correctness of the information obtained through the experiment and their objectivity can be ensured when all the important conditions are fulfilled (conditions for experimenting, the correct choice of the object, and the correct determination of the problems that are considered important to solve). Researches with applied characteristics in public administration help to analyze the attitude of those who are asked for their opinion on the actions and speeches of all the leaders in different concrete conditions. Although such analyses do not provide detailed information about the public administration system, they act as an important tool for collecting and systematizing real materials to make theoretical generalizations and obtain results in the sphere of public administration. It is impossible in real life to suddenly change the state and the main organizational structures of the state. As an example, it is impossible to establish and form a parliament and form a government within the country, provided that other

conditions are met. It is also impossible to calculate their effectiveness and compare them. Public administration is a macro-level management system. The application of these methods allows for reduction of the science in the field of public administration from the macro-level of analysis to the micro-level, to study the opposing persons in the sphere of public administration, their behavior, and activity directions. Historical types of the state, grouping of state regimes, and other approaches are developed through these methods. The application of methods that are considered specific for social sciences in the public administration system requires the determination and use of their qualities specific to public administration. As an example, it can be shown that when using the comparison method, along with the quantitative analysis of the compared phenomena, showing the aspects of their qualities, taking into account this difference in quality, it is necessary to continue the process. Undoubtedly, it should be noted that other unnamed methods are also used in the management system. However, none of these methods alone is sufficient for quality management. Thus, the use of those methods together, that is, in a complex manner, can determine the successful implementation of public administration. In addition, it is impossible to apply all of the numerous methods available in public administration at the same level. According to experts, it is not necessary. In general, many of the different methods are applied with some features and limitations in certain specific conditions. In German scientific literature, it is stated that public administration is implemented by two methods. The first method is the negative method. According to the first method, judicial transactions with legislative bodies are related to the operations carried out by public administration subjects by the concept of separation of powers in the classical form. In the positive method of public administration, the legislative power and the judiciary are interested in the management activity at a certain level.

The necessity of using a modern approach to the state's personnel policy, which is applied in many developed countries in modern times, was first proposed by scientists from Great Britain and Australia. Today, not the authoritarian management regime and its methods, but democratic management is applied both in the enterprises operating in the private sector and the public sector institutions. Therefore, it is necessary to eliminate the hierarchical and unilateral application of power.

Civil service

The method of total quality improvement, which is of special importance in the civil service, was first applied in England during the Thatcher period, and then in other countries. Programs based on this method are applied in civil service human resources policy in countries such as Great Britain, Canada, and New Zealand. The professionalism of a civil servant depends on his continuous development and adaptation to new requirements for work. In parallel with innovations, the principle of succession is always on the agenda. State body managers must preserve the knowledge and experience that have been applied for many years while adopting the innovations applied in both specific professional

knowledge and broad management abilities. According to the law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On Civil Service", (2) there are grounds for the appointment of a civil servant to a higher position, inclusion in the list of reserve personnel of the civil service, the result of the assessment of the civil servant's service activity, and personal initiative for further education of the civil servant. Further education of the civil servant is carried out in professional development and retraining institutions, relevant structures created in educational institutions, internship and professional training courses, and other institutions that have been specially approved for their activities in this field in the directions determined by legislation. Civil servants can be sent to foreign countries for further education. A network of special training institutions can be established to ensure continuous development and improvement of civil servants. It is possible to apply this process remotely during the pandemic period and on the eve of the next one. The main motive for attracting civil servants to participate in these trainings is promotion and individual career planning. That is, the conducted pieces of training and further education programs are based on a certain result. For example, in the US practice, each civil servant has individual career goal plans. Taking into account that the activity of the mentioned training centers is at the expense of certain time and financial resources, in this case, benefits should be provided by the funds spent. Therefore, these pieces of training can be improved in the direction of specific deficiencies. Selections are made for trainees in several advanced practices. The state body determines the need for training among civil servants.

It is impossible to imagine modern administrative management and public services without computers and technical tools. The technical knowledge of employees of state bodies must be constantly updated, therefore it is important to organize such courses for employees who have difficulty using computers and other software and technical tools. Pieces of training take place locally within the organization, in special centers, and also in foreign countries in the form of internships. Internships in foreign countries and practical learning of advanced practice are more motivating for employees. For this, special competitions can be announced and the winners of these competitions can be sent to training at the expense of the state.

We can show the skills and habits to be inculcated in the training in the following 2 groups: general skills: to involve the employees in the internship and trial period to the general legislation, ethics, accountability, ICT skills course; personal and professional development.

Along with increasing the professionalism of civil servants, which is the main goal of the training, it is also important to raise their moral and psychological level. The active participation of civil servants in these trainings, and the quantitative and qualitative indicators of their activities before and after the training should be evaluated. In this case, the quality of work of civil servants increases, and indirectly, the activity of the state institution increases.

In the Federal Republic of Germany, high financial incentives and bonus systems are applied in additional education programs for civil servants. The purpose of pieces of training for the development of civil servants in the public human resources practice of the Republic of Turkey is the advancement of civil servants in the service. In this case, appointments are also made to vacant positions. Implementation of special pieces of training for managers would be an adequate step. To adapt the activities of the educational centers operating under the state bodies to the requirements of the time, a plan of action should be prepared, the experience of the educational centers of the state bodies should be studied and proposals related to their future activities should be prepared, and a coordination body should be established to coordinate the activities of the educational centers.

Academy of Public Administration operates under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan to train and improve the professionalism of civil servants. Additional educational programs for the development of civil servants are implemented in the academy for a period of 2 or 3 years.

To increase the efficiency of the activities of civil servants, since 2016, the implementation of the project "Support to Civil Service Training in the Republic of Azerbaijan" has been started in the Academy within the framework of the cooperation of the Central European Union and the UN IP. The main goal of the project is to strengthen the management and coordination of training and professional development functions of civil servants. Civil servants in our republic have the right to engage in scientific and creative activities. The main point that forms professionalism is the unity of theoretical and practical knowledge. Therefore, it is useful to stimulate civil servants in scientific activity. Priority is given to persons with scientific activity in the classification of civil service in Canada from advanced experiences.

Reforms in this field in the Republic of Azerbaijan

In the Republic of Azerbaijan, there is a need for intra-organizational and inter-organizational functional reforms and a reduction of diversification of authority. In the developed countries of the world, the practice of certification is used when internal authority reforms are implemented. In the Republic of Azerbaijan, the functions and duties of institutions are sometimes duplicated. An example of this is the existence of gaps in the division of powers between local executive authorities and local self-government bodies. This problem is one of the main factors affecting the professionalism of employees in those bodies.

In recent years, we have seen the example of bringing or coordinating bodies in the Republic of Azerbaijan as a positive case. On October 22, 2019, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the Ministry of Taxes of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the State Committee for Property Issues of the Republic of Azerbaijan, and the State Agency for Antimonopoly and Consumer Market Control of the Republic of Azerbaijan were included in the structure of the Ministry of Economy of the Republic of

Azerbaijan in the status of relevant public services. Another example in the Republic of Azerbaijan is the example of "ASAN Service". In these centers, under the State Agency for Citizen Service and Social Innovation under the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, the services provided by the state bodies are provided in a unified and coordinated manner. By making such a division, corruption and bureaucratic monopoly are avoided. It is acceptable to establish horizontal relations between the specified public services and to implement inter-sectoral coordination programs. The acquisition of special communication skills by the employees of ASAN service centers attracts the attention of citizens. To master this professional characteristic, 2-directional pieces of training aimed at improving behavior and increasing knowledge are conducted. Conducting these trainings created an idea of the behavior expected of a modern civil servant.

The "volunteer mechanisms" established in the basic ASAN Service are the beginning of professional personnel training for institutions, as well as a chance for young people to adapt to the work environment and the public service sector.

The problem of unemployment among young people due to macroeconomic problems in our country has been decreasing in recent years. It is necessary to encourage young professionals to serve in the civil service in the labor market and to use their potential properly.

Relations in state institutions

One of the main factors affecting the psychological state and professionalism of employees in state institutions is the corporate environment. The management of the state body plays an important role in regulating these relations. It is beneficial for the productivity of the institution to establish the basis of relations in public institutions on cooperation, working for a common principle, and organizing healthy competition. Sometimes civil servants have the idea that the state body operates at the expense of the state budget, and therefore there is no possibility of the body going bankrupt, so even if there is no profitability ratio, it will not lose its job. But this is wrong and harmful thinking. Individual and interdepartmental communication in state institutions should always be strong, and intersectoral coordination should complement the authority of the institution. In modern management, it is useful to have healthy conflicts within the organization. Special methods are used for conflict management and regulation in the state institution.

Among the features that determine the professional activity of civil servants, transparency and accountability occupy an important place. Accountability of the activities of civil servants also means accountability of the state and the institution. In Azerbaijan, there was no mechanism of direct accountability to citizens in the administrative emirate management regime. However, since the Republic of Azerbaijan has a democratic management system after gaining independence, accountability is manifested both horizontally and vertically.

A public servant's attitude to ethical values is another element of his professionalism. In the Republic

of Azerbaijan, the law "On Ethical Behavior of Civil Servants" defines the professional service behavior of civil servants. Before making administrative decisions, civil servants must predict the consequences of their decisions and take personal responsibility. No administrative success can be achieved without ethical rules and accountability. Civil servants must follow the rules of ethical behavior in every case. In some cases, ethical dilemmas are experienced in public administration, in which case, one should be able to evaluate his behavior legally and ethically.

In modern times, the basis of management is correct, adequate, and objective information. The civil servant must exchange this information when necessary and use the service information in a timely and correct manner. One of the features that indicate the level of knowledge of a modern civil servant is the use of electronic databases and cybersecurity knowledge. It is necessary to have skills in the electronic government model, which forms the basis of modern management and public administration. For this purpose, the adoption of the decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On some measures in the field of the provision of electronic services by state bodies" dated May 23, 2011, as well as the establishment of relevant institutions by the President of the country, are of particular importance. It is necessary to communicate with business institutions, citizens, and non-governmental organizations and standardize public relations on such platforms.

The ability of civil servants to adapt to the situation affects their professional performance. This is the basic principle of the "situation approach", which is one of the two main approaches in modern management in the middle of the last century. Another modern management approach is the stress approach, where planning, discipline, and analysis come to the fore. Let's distinguish 3 types of workers according to the adaptation model:

- Adaptation of a new and inexperienced employee;
- Experienced, but new employee in the collective or institution;
- Adaptation of elderly people to use modern-innovative technologies.

Based on the model of meritocracy, which is widely applied in public administration, let us note that the case of nepotism in admission and promotion in the civil service should be strictly avoided. In such cases, both the "benefited" person is not interested in his personal development, and the motivation of other employees who observe this situation decreases. This, in a complex case, lowers the level of professionalism of the state institution, and citizens' confidence in the body decreases. Civil servants cannot be discriminated against on any grounds. In this regard, there are a few problems in the Republic of Azerbaijan. Thus, there is no case of gender-religious-racial-ethnic discrimination.

One of the main reasons for the development of the public sector in European countries is the Excellence model created by the applied "Quality Management Authority". This model consists of 2 groups and

9 basic criteria. Among these criteria, the application of which will be useful for our country is as follows:

- resource management,
- leadership qualities,
- the unity of civil servants' satisfaction and citizen's satisfaction.

It is appropriate to use various surveys and special meetings so that civil servants can easily express their opinions and suggestions about the activity and improvement of state institutions. With this, not only the work activity of individual individuals but also the work activity of the institution and civil service will be improved. That is, the civil servant will feel important in both micro and macro sense and this is good for his motivation. The improvement of the quality of work of civil servants and the development of civil service careers directly depend on themselves and the state institution. Each employee should decide which powers he likes as a staff, which field of work he is more capable of, and which benefit he brings to the organization. State institutions should constantly support the development of employees. It would be useful to have psychological analysis centers within state institutions. We can show the job functions of these business-psychological analysis centers in the following order:

- Determine the professional goals of the employees and align them with the goals of the institution;
- Having goals for departments and sectors;
- Ensuring work for common principles;
- To eliminate situations that hinder the professional development of employees;
- To analyze the social values of employees;
- Determine special skills and talents of employees;
- Implementing motivational programs;
- To evaluate the work performance of the collective, individual departments and sectors, civil servants;
- To carry out changes of authority for testing and to give difficult tasks;
- Constant analysis of citizens' opinions;
- Permanent analyses of public servants about the institution and duties, etc.

Human resource centers can be created for a modern approach to civil service personnel policy. As a special category of DOST centers in the Republic of Azerbaijan from August 9, 2018, centers providing services related to civil service human resources and labor activity would be useful. Application of the competency model in public administration is one of the urgent issues. Since American experts are supporters of a more "personal" approach, they limit the scope of the concept of competence either to personal qualities or to knowledge, skills, and abilities and call it KSAO: Knowledge, Skills, Ability, Other characteristics. One of the most common mistakes made is to mistake these features or to ignore any of them altogether. However, the full development of the employee in management should be applied equally to each. An item that constitutes a relative or absolute weakness should have a special development program tailored to the individual and an inter-assessment analysis should be carried out. One of the main purposes

of this is to see if the 4 nuances we listed show changes over time.

The purpose of evaluating the service activity of a civil servant in the Republic of Azerbaijan is to evaluate the performance of his duties during the calendar year, to fulfill the requirements of his position, and to determine the future development of the civil servant. Based on the results of the assessment of the service activity, the head of the state body may include the civil servant in the list of reserve personnel for management positions and incentive measures may be taken. If it is unsatisfactory, the issue of his transfer to a lower administrative position is considered. Many models are used here - interview, result-based, and goal-setting management methods. In Great Britain, criteria such as goals, decision-making, and communication are taken as the basis for evaluation. Skills such as employee-manager relations and adaptability are also undervalued in Denmark. In France, technical skills are of particular importance, in Slovenia there are criteria such as creativity and initiative. In addition, daily and quarterly inspections can also have a positive effect on the annual result. In our country, direct supervision of the performance evaluation of public servants is a bureaucratic obstacle. Many countries use such external audit systems. To increase the professionalism of civil servants, motivational measures are necessary and the rewarding is grouped materially and morally. One of the material factors affecting the motivation of civil servants is salary. According to the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on "Civil Service" (2), the amount of government salary given to civil servants depends on the scope of authority, degree of responsibility, the required level of professionalism, and length of service. As a pilot project, a differential salary system can be established in any government agency.

Conclusion

The professionalism of civil servants cannot be considered a stable concept. The presence of intensive changes in the labor market and management from year to year also affects the professionals. A comprehensive approach to the professionalism of civil servants should be applied. Although this is a complex mechanism, the outcome will affect social welfare. It will be effective if the "re-training" specialty is cre-

ated in the state bodies that carry out personnel training and public manager training, and old employees are involved in this training. In all these measures, the aim should be not only to identify weaknesses and deficiencies but also to identify good performance. To evaluate the performance of civil servants, it is necessary to have an independent audit experience and reward based on non-material incentives.

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